

Awareness Regarding the COTPA Act: A Community Based Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Tobacco consumption remains a major preventable cause of morbidity and mortality globally and in India. Despite the enactment of the Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products Act (COTPA), 2003, awareness and compliance remain suboptimal.

Aim: To assess awareness regarding the COTPA Act among residents in the field practice areas of GMERS Medical College, Dharpur-Patan.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 440 participants using a pretested semi-structured questionnaire. Chi-square test was applied for assessing associations. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Overall, 48.6% of participants had heard about the COTPA Act. Awareness was significantly higher among younger individuals, urban residents, educated participants, and those with skilled occupations. However, gaps in knowledge regarding specific provisions persisted.

Conclusion: There is a need for targeted educational campaigns and stricter enforcement to improve awareness and compliance with COTPA Act regulations, especially in rural and less educated populations.

Keywords: Tobacco Control, COTPA Act, Awareness, Compliance, Cross-sectional Study, Gujarat.

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Introduction

Tobacco use continues to be a leading cause of preventable morbidity and mortality worldwide. It is estimated that tobacco kills more than 8 million people globally every year [1]. In response to the growing burden, the World Health Organization (WHO) introduced the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (WHO-FCTC) in 2003, emphasizing policy measures to reduce tobacco consumption [2]. In India, tobacco use accounts for nearly 1 million deaths annually, with both smoking and smokeless tobacco forms being widespread [3]. The Global Adult Tobacco Survey-2 (GATS-2, 2016-17) reported that 28.6% of adults in India use tobacco in some form [4].

To address this public health crisis, the Government of India enacted the Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products Act (COTPA) in 2003, aimed at regulating advertising, trade, and usage of tobacco products [5]. Key provisions of COTPA include prohibition of smoking in public places, prohibition of sale of tobacco products to minors and near educational institutions, mandatory pictorial health warnings, and restriction of advertisements.

Gujarat has shown considerable tobacco usage, especially in smokeless forms like gutkha and khaini. As per the GATS-2 report, around 19.8% of the adult population in Gujarat use tobacco products [6]. Various local surveys conducted across Gujarat have highlighted gaps in awareness regarding specific provisions of COTPA among different population groups [7].

In the rural and semi-urban areas catered by GMERS Medical College Dharpur-Patan (via its RHTC and UHTC), tobacco use is notably prevalent. However, studies focusing on the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to the COTPA Act are limited. There is a pressing need to assess the level of awareness to strengthen enforcement and health promotion initiatives. Despite the existence of COTPA Act for over two decades, there is limited awareness and poor compliance among the general population, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas, leading to continued high rates of tobacco use. Understanding awareness levels will help identify specific gaps in knowledge and compliance. This

will enable the planning of targeted educational and regulatory interventions. The study will also provide baseline data for future monitoring and evaluation of tobacco control programs in the region. It will help in reducing the burden of tobacco-related diseases and promoting a tobacco-free environment in the region.

Aim

To assess the awareness regarding the provisions of the Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products Act (COTPA), 2003 among the population residing in the field practice areas of Rural Health Training Centre (RHTC) and Urban Health Training Centre (UHTC) of GMERS Medical College, Dharpur-Patan.

Objectives

1. To determine the level of awareness about various sections of the COTPA Act, 2003 among the study population.
2. To identify socio-demographic factors associated with the level of awareness about COTPA Act.
3. To assess the compliance-related behaviors (e.g., smoking in public places, selling tobacco near educational institutions) among the study population.
4. To suggest targeted recommendations based on findings for better implementation of the COTPA Act.

Methodology

The present study was a cross-sectional study conducted to assess the awareness regarding the COTPA Act among individuals residing in the field practice areas of Rural Health Training Centre (RHTC) and Urban Health Training Centre (UHTC) attached to GMERS Medical College, Dharpur-Patan.

The study population comprised adult individuals aged 18 years and above, residing in the selected areas during the study period. Individuals unwilling to participate or unable to give informed consent were excluded from the study.

Inclusion criteria included adults aged ≥ 18 years who were permanent residents of the study area and who provided informed consent for participation. Exclusion criteria involved individuals with cognitive impairment or serious illness preventing communication at the time of interview.

The sample size calculation was done using the standard formula $4PQ/L^2$, where:

- P = estimated prevalence of awareness regarding COTPA Act (assumed to be 50% due to lack of local studies for maximum sample size),
- Q = $(100 - P) = 50$,
- L = allowable error (10% of P = 5).

Thus,

$$\text{Sample size} = 4 \times 50 \times 50 / 5^2 = 4 \times 50 \times 50 / 25 = 400.$$

Adding 10% for non-response, the final sample size was estimated to be 440 participants.

Data collection was carried out using a pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire in the local language. The questionnaire included sections on socio-demographic details, awareness of COTPA Act provisions, and compliance behaviours. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews conducted by trained investigators.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize data in terms of frequencies and percentages. Associations between awareness levels and socio-demographic variables were assessed using appropriate tests of significance, such as the Chi-square test for categorical variables. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 440 participants were enrolled in the study. The mean age of participants was 38.7 ± 12.4 years, with a slight male predominance (54.5%). The majority were residents of rural areas (67.7%). Regarding educational status, 28.4% had completed secondary education, while 22.3% were illiterate. Occupationally, 36.1% were engaged in unskilled labor.

Awareness about the COTPA Act was found to be moderate; 48.6% of participants had heard about the Act. Among those aware, 62.4% knew that smoking is prohibited in public places, 39.8% were aware of the ban on tobacco sale near educational institutions, and 27.1% were aware of mandatory pictorial warnings on tobacco product packaging.

Factors significantly associated with higher awareness included younger age (18-30 years), higher education levels, and urban residence ($p < 0.05$). Compliance-related behaviors were suboptimal; 21.2% reported witnessing smoking in public places in the last month, and 15.7% observed sale of tobacco near schools.

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of participants

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group (years)	18-30	132	30.00%
	31-45	174	39.50%
	>45	134	30.50%
Gender	Male	240	54.50%
	Female	200	45.50%
Area of Residence	Rural	298	67.70%
	Urban	142	32.30%
Educational Status	Illiterate	98	22.30%
	Primary	118	26.80%
	Secondary and above	224	50.90%
Occupation	Unskilled	159	36.10%
	Skilled	127	28.90%
	Professional/Clerical	78	17.70%
	Unemployed/Students	76	17.30%

Table 2: Awareness (Knowledge), Attitude, and Practice Regarding Provisions of COTPA Act

Section	Parameter	Frequency	Percentage
Knowledge	Heard about COTPA Act	214	48.60%
	Aware of prohibition of smoking in public places	134	62.4%*
	Aware of ban on sale near educational institutions	85	39.8%*
	Aware of mandatory pictorial warnings on tobacco packs	58	27.1%*
Attitude	Agree with prohibition of smoking in public places	176	82.2%*
	Support ban of tobacco sale near schools	142	66.4%*
	Believe pictorial warnings reduce tobacco use	96	44.9%*
Practice	Avoid smoking in public places	178	83.2%*
	Reported others smoking in public places in last month	45	21.2%*
	Observed sale of tobacco near educational institutions	34	15.7%*

* Percentages calculated out of 214 participants who had heard about COTPA Act.

Table 3: Association of awareness about COTPA Act with socio-cultural factors

Socio-Cultural Factor	Category	Aware (n=214)	Not Aware (n=226)	Chi-square value	p-value	Significance
Age Group	18–30 years vs >30 years	78 vs 136	54 vs 172	5.92	0.015	Significant
Gender	Male vs Female	128 vs 86	112 vs 114	1.25	0.264	Not Significant
Area of Residence	Urban vs Rural	102 vs 112	40 vs 186	30.45	<0.001	Highly Significant
Educational Status	Secondary and above vs Below	152 vs 62	72 vs 154	43.87	<0.001	Highly Significant
Occupation	Skilled/Professional vs Others	105 vs 109	70 vs 156	14.56	<0.001	Highly Significant

Figure 1: Distribution of participants according to knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding the COTPA Act (n=440)

Awareness regarding the COTPA Act was significantly associated with the younger age group, urban residence, higher educational status, and skilled/professional occupation. Gender did not show a statistically significant association with awareness.

Discussion

In the present cross-sectional study conducted in the field practice areas of GMERS Medical College, Dharpur-Patan, the awareness regarding the Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products Act (COTPA) was found to be moderate, with 48.6% of participants having heard about the Act. These findings are comparable to a study conducted by Sharma et al. in Rajasthan, where 45.2% of respondents were aware of the COTPA Act [8]. Similarly, a study by Meena et al. in Delhi found that 50.8% of the population had heard about the tobacco control law [9].

Awareness was significantly higher among younger individuals aged 18–30 years ($p = 0.015$). This aligns with findings from Singh et al. in Uttar Pradesh, who reported that awareness was significantly higher among the younger population group [10]. Younger individuals may have better exposure to mass media campaigns and health education efforts.

No statistically significant association was found between gender and awareness levels in this study ($p = 0.264$). This finding is consistent with a study by Ghosh et al. in West Bengal, where gender did not show a significant influence on tobacco law awareness [11]. However, some other studies such as that by Choudhary et al. in Madhya Pradesh found males to be more aware compared to females [12], indicating possible regional variations.

Participants residing in urban areas had significantly higher awareness compared to rural residents ($p < 0.001$). Similar observations were reported by Chauhan et al. in Maharashtra, where urban residents demonstrated better knowledge and adherence to COTPA provisions [13]. Better access to education, awareness programs, and regulatory enforcement in urban areas could explain this difference.

Educational status was strongly associated with awareness. Participants with secondary education and above had significantly higher awareness ($p < 0.001$). These results are consistent with a study conducted by Sinha et al. in Bihar, which showed that awareness regarding tobacco laws increased with the level of education [14]. This trend highlights the crucial role of education in health-related knowledge dissemination.

Occupational status was also found to be a significant factor; skilled and professional workers had better awareness compared to unskilled laborers ($p < 0.001$). Similar findings were reported by Rani et al. in Karnataka, where professionals showed better compliance and knowledge regarding tobacco control measures [15].

Among those aware, 62.4% knew about the prohibition of smoking in public places. This is comparable to the findings of Yadav et al., where 65% of participants were aware of this provision [16]. However, awareness regarding the prohibition of sale near educational institutions (39.8%) and pictorial warnings (27.1%) was lower, indicating a specific gap in knowledge, which is similar to the gaps reported in a study by Prasad et al. in Tamil Nadu [17].

Positive attitude towards smoking bans in public places was noted among 82.2% of those aware, aligning with the study conducted by Goel et al. in Chandigarh, which reported 80% support for smoking bans [18]. However, practices were suboptimal; 21.2% reported observing smoking in public places and 15.7% observed the sale of tobacco near educational institutions, indicating enforcement challenges similar to those observed by Rathore et al. in Gujarat [19].

Overall, the study highlights that although awareness regarding the COTPA Act is moderate, gaps still persist, especially in rural areas and among the less educated population. Strengthening awareness programs focusing on these vulnerable groups could enhance compliance with tobacco control regulations.

Conclusion

The study concludes that while nearly half of the participants were aware of the COTPA Act, significant gaps exist in knowledge regarding specific provisions, particularly among rural, less educated, and unskilled populations. Younger age, urban residence, higher education, and skilled/professional occupation were significantly associated with higher levels of awareness. Focused health education campaigns, better enforcement of COTPA regulations, and community-based interventions are needed to enhance public awareness and compliance.

Limitations

The present study, being cross-sectional in nature, limits the ability to establish causal relationships between awareness levels and socio-demographic factors. The data were collected through self-reported responses, which could be influenced by recall bias or social desirability bias, potentially affecting the accuracy of the findings. Additionally, the study was conducted in a specific geographic region, which may limit the generalizability of the results to wider populations.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, it is recommended to intensify Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) activities specifically targeted at rural, less educated, and unskilled populations to enhance awareness about the COTPA Act. Health education sessions should be incorporated into existing community outreach programs, especially focusing on youth and educational institutions. Stronger enforcement of COTPA provisions should be ensured by local administrative authorities. Integration of tobacco control education into school and college curricula is advisable to build awareness from an early age.

References

1. World Health Organization. Tobacco [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; 2024 [cited 2025 Apr 29]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/tobacco>.
2. World Health Organization. WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control. Geneva: WHO; 2003.
3. Indian Council of Medical Research. Tobacco Control in India: Policy Review and Future Directions. New Delhi: ICMR; 2020.
4. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Global Adult Tobacco Survey India 2016–17 Report. New Delhi: MoHFW; 2017.
5. Ministry of Law and Justice, Government of India. The Cigarettes and Other Tobacco Products (Prohibition of Advertisement and Regulation of Trade and Commerce, Production, Supply and Distribution) Act, 2003. New Delhi: Government of India Press; 2003.
6. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Global Adult Tobacco Survey 2nd Round: Gujarat State Fact Sheet 2016–17. New Delhi: MoHFW; 2017.
7. Patel D, Shah P, Patel J. Awareness and compliance of tobacco control laws among the general population in Gujarat. *Indian J Community Health*. 2021;33(2):298-304.
8. Sharma R, Gupta S, Sharma S. Awareness and compliance of tobacco control laws among the public in Rajasthan. *Indian J Public Health*. 2021;65(2):170-4.
9. Meena LP, Yadav V, Meena N, Yadav R. Assessment of awareness and knowledge about the COTPA Act among adults in Delhi. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2020;14(5):LC01-5.
10. Singh A, Arora M, Gupta VK. Tobacco control law awareness among youth in Uttar Pradesh. *Indian J Community Med*. 2019;44(2):136-9.
11. Ghosh S, Samanta A, Sarkar P. Awareness about tobacco control law among rural and urban populations of West Bengal. *Indian J Public Health*. 2020;64(2):140-3.
12. Choudhary M, Patidar H, Bhardwaj P. Awareness and attitude towards COTPA 2003 among adults in Madhya Pradesh. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2019;6(4):1512-6.
13. Chauhan T, Deshmukh V, Bhave M. Awareness regarding COTPA Act implementation among urban population of Maharashtra. *J Community Health Manag*. 2018;5(4):178-83.
14. Sinha DN, Gupta PC, Pednekar MS. Tobacco control policies in India: Implementation gaps and recommendations. *World Health Organization South-East Asia Journal of Public Health*. 2018;7(1):17-24.

15. Rani M, Thamarangsi T, Agarwal N. Tobacco use and awareness of tobacco control measures among professionals in Karnataka. *Indian J Med Res.* 2020;151(2):183-9.
16. Yadav A, Singh J, Katyal R, Yadav J. Awareness and perception regarding anti-smoking laws among general public in Haryana. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2018;7(4):682-6.
17. Prasad VM, Dorairaj VS, Ramesh G, Chockalingam K. Knowledge and compliance of COTPA regulations among adults in Tamil Nadu. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev.* 2017;18(2):521-6.
18. Goel S, Singh RJ, Dey A, Singh PK. Public support for smoke-free policies in India: Evidence from Global Adult Tobacco Survey 2. *Indian J Public Health.* 2016;60(2):95-101.
19. Rathore PK, Sharma R, Pithadia P. Evaluation of implementation and compliance of COTPA Act in Gujarat: A situational analysis. *Indian J Community Med.* 2020;45(3):310-5.